

MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF LOCAL TURKISH CIRGALAN PEPPER GENOTYPES VIA SRAP MARKERS

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ABSTRACT. Cırgalan pepper is a local cultivar that has been grown in Kayseri for many years, consumed as powdered pepper after being dried and has essential value for the spice market. However, these cultivars have lost their production areas because of yield and quality losses. As in other local varieties, the variety in question also shows significant variation in production areas due to open pollination. It is essential to establish breeding programs to utilize the existing variation in local varieties and to increase yield and quality parameters. The first stage of pepper breeding is the characterization of present genotypes. In this study, molecular characterization of genotypes of Cırgalan pepper collected from pepper production areas of Kayseri province was aimed. In this study, 32 pepper genotypes were subjected to DNA analysis using 14 SRAP primer combinations, identifying 79 total bands. The highest number of bands was obtained from the primer combination Me13-Em14 (9), while the lowest number of bands was obtained from the primer combinations Me9-Em6 and Me12-Em8 (3). The average polymorphism rate was 29.3%, with the highest polymorphism rate observed for the Me12-Em4 primer combination (60%). The PIC values of the markers varied broadly, from 0,01 (for primer combination Me9-Em6) to 0,51 (Me13-Em14), with a mean of 0.30. Genetic similarity was determined between 0.67-1.00. This study showed genetic differences among Cırgalan pepper genotypes produced in the Kayseri region. With breeding programs in light of these results, it can be helpful to increase production areas of this cultivar, which was adopted in the Kayseri region after obtaining disease resistance, in addition to improving the yield and quality of this cultivar.

Keywords: *Capsicum annuum*, *Cırgalan pepper*, *SRAP*, *molecular characterization*

INTRODUCTION

Anatolia, situated in one of the regions where agriculture was first practiced globally, has become the genetic center of numerous cultivated plant species. Additionally, the rate of plant endemism is high. To maintain the sustainability of crop production, it is imperative to preserve the diversity of plant genetic resources of cultivated species [1]. However, due to natural disasters such as fire and erosion, hybrid varieties are replacing native varieties in the population, urbanization and development works, changes in agricultural systems, and agricultural control practices. As a result of this realization, studies have been initiated in many countries to identify, protect, and conserve plant resources [2]. Pepper is one of the five significant vegetables consumed extensively in various forms throughout the world. *Capsicum annuum* L., a vegetable native to hot climates, has a $2n=24$ chromosome structure and is highly self-pollinating [3]. Pepper is cultivated in almost all regions of Turkey. In addition to fresh consumption, it is used in many ways in pepper powder, tomato paste, roasted meat, sauce, pickles, and main dishes [4]. Furthermore, pepper juice, mainly derived from hot peppers, is a widely utilized ingredient in the food industry [5]. Pepper is also a valuable dietary component, offering vitamins A, B, C, and E and antioxidant properties [5]; [6]. Capsaicin (C₁₈H₂₇O₃N), the

compound responsible for pepper's pungency, facilitates digestion and enhances absorption by stimulating gastric and intestinal motility [7]. Approximately 31 million tons of pepper are produced annually, with Turkey accounting for approximately 2.1 million tons. Turkey ranks sixth in vegetable production, following tomatoes, watermelons, onions, melons, and cucumbers.

Turkey has been ranked second worldwide for pepper production several times after China. However, it has been ranked fourth in other years, replacing Indonesia [8]. The green pepper production of the Central Anatolia region is 6,058 tons in 5,950 da, while the green pepper production of Kayseri province is 353 tons in 598 da [9]. Pepper, which exhibits a wide range of morphological-agronomic characteristics in both fruit and plant, is consumed in various ways, depending on the specific characteristics of the fruit in question [10]. Selections and open pollination were applied to the local populations grown by producers in terms of consumer demands and yield. In the pepper grown one-year-old in Turkey conditions, variations in plant and fruit structure were observed, thus increasing the number of genotypes in the country and plant genetic resources daily. One of our country's most significant genetic resources is the standard pepper variety known as the Cırgalan pepper, cultivated in the Kayseri and its surrounding regions. The Cırgalan pepper is characterized by its flag-red color, height of approximately 7 cm, and four lobes. It constitutes a significant portion of the pepper production in Kayseri and its surrounding provinces. After drying, the Cırgalan pepper is consumed as powdered pepper. It has considerable value in the spice market, especially in the Kayseri region. As production is low, spice shops explain that Cırgalan pepper is being replaced by peppers from other regions and sold as powdered pepper. Although Cırgalan pepper is of high quality, productivity has decreased significantly. Production has been limited to a very small area due to the introduction of diseases and pests not previously found in the region. Furthermore, the observed decline in quality and yield suggests that the local Cırgalan pepper will become unproductive over time. In recent years, there has been a rapid transition to cultivating F1 hybrid varieties in Turkey, while local pepper production with standard seeds has remained in local areas. With the acceleration of local seed production in Turkey, local varieties for both standard and F1 hybrid seeds have also gained momentum. To achieve this objective, it is first necessary to collect and characterize the local genetic resources in question. Once this has been done, they can be bred as a standard variety to eliminate some of the associated drawbacks. In the context of breeding studies, the initial step is characterization. Morphological characterization has certain limitations in accurately identifying accessions, including a limited number of traits to characterize [11], highly heritable traits demonstrating no variation across a significant portion of the material studied [12], and trait expression being strongly influenced by environmental factors, particularly in quantitative traits [12,11]. DNA markers are invaluable tools for measuring the diversity of plant species. In 1997, it was demonstrated that the number of traits that can be used to identify accessions is limited accurately, that traits are highly heritable, and that trait expression is subjected to environmental solid influence, mainly in quantitative traits. DNA markers are indispensable tools for measuring the diversity of plant species. The assay's cost, the hardware's affordability, throughput, convenience, and ease of assay development and automation are essential factors when choosing a technology. Many marker techniques are available for PGR characterization, including RAPD, AFLP, SSR, SNP, SRAP, etc. SRAP markers should be viewed as analogous to morphological character states, which have been widely used in the delimitation and assessment of variation within and between individuals [13-16].

SRAP markers target coding regions of the genome [17], and markers are more potent for revealing genetic diversity among closely related cultivars than SSR, ISSR, or RAPD markers [18]. They can also be used for linkage map construction [19], genomic and cDNA fingerprinting, gene tagging, genetic diversity analysis [17], map-based cloning [20], hybrid identification [21], and sex determination [22]. The present study aimed to characterize different Cırgalan pepper genotypes obtained from the center and districts of Kayseri province with the SRAP marker system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the study, 23 Cırgalan peppers, 2 Capia peppers, 2 Maraş peppers, and 1 green pepper genotype were used as controls (Table 1).

Table 1. Pepper genotypes used in the study

S. N.	Genotype Code	Variety	Collected Location
1	ERU1	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
2	ERU 2	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
3	ERU 3	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
4	ERU 4	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
5	ERU 5	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
6	ERU 6	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
7	ERU 7	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
9	ERU 9	Cırgalan Pepper	Cırgalan district
11	ERU 11	Cırgalan Pepper	Erkilet district
12	ERU 15	Cırgalan Pepper	Erkilet district
13	ERU 17	Cırgalan Pepper	Erkilet district
15	ERU 20	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
16	ERU 918	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
17	ERU 919	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
19	ERU 926	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
20	ERU 929	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
21	ERU 931	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
22	ERU 933	Cırgalan Pepper	Yamula district
23	ERU 934	Cırgalan Pepper	Develi district
24	ERU 937	Cırgalan Pepper	Develi district
25	ERU 941	Cırgalan Pepper	Develi district
26	ERU 942	Cırgalan Pepper	Develi district
27	ERU 2000	Cırgalan Pepper	Develi district
28	ERU 1250	Capia Pepper	F1 Hybrid
29	ERU 1257	Capia Pepper	F1 Hybrid
30	ERU 1258	Green Pepper	F1 Hybrid
31	ERU KM1	Maraş Pepper	Kahramanmaraş
32	ERU KM2	Maraş Pepper	Kahramanmaraş

Molecular Characterization

14 SRAP primer combinations were used in molecular characterization. A polymerase chain reaction (PCR) reaction for SRAP was conducted in a 15- μ l volume containing 1.5 μ l of template DNA, 7.5 μ l of PCR master mix (2x), 1.5 μ l of diluted primer, and 3.5 μ l of nuclease-free water. The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was conducted with the following thermal profile: an initial denaturation at 94 °C for 5 min, followed by five cycles of 1 min at 94 °C (denaturation), 1 min at 35 °C (annealing), and 1 min at 72 °C (extension). The temperature was then lowered to 2 °C (extension). This was followed by 35 cycles of 1 min at 94 °C (denaturation), 1 min at 50 °C (annealing), and 1 min at 72 °C (extension). Finally, a final extension at 72 °C for 10 min was performed. Following the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) procedure, the amplified deoxyribonucleic acids (DNAs) were electrophoresed in 2% agarose gel (containing ethidium bromide) with the use of 1X Tris-borate-ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (TBE) buffer at 120 volts for 120 minutes. The amplified bands were then visualized and imaged under ultraviolet (UV) light. Gel images were scored and analyzed using the NTSYS (Numerical Taxonomy Multivariate Analysis System) computer package program. PIC was calculated using PIC calculator as Jan, [23].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 32 pepper genotypes were subjected to DNA analysis using 14 SRAP primer combinations, identifying 79 distinct bands. The highest number of bands was obtained from the primer combination Me13-Em14 (9), while the lowest number of bands was obtained from the primer combinations Me9-Em6 and Me12-Em8 (3). The average polymorphism rate was 29.3%, with the highest polymorphism rate observed for the Me12-Em4 primer combination (60%). The PIC values of the markers varied broadly, from 0,01 (for primer combination Me9-Em6) to 0,51 (Me13-Em14), with a mean of 0.30 (Table 2.)

Table 2. Performance of the 14 SRAP marker combinations to estimate the genetic diversity parameters of the pepper genotypes.

Primer Combinations	Total band number	Polimorphic band number	Polimophisim Ratio(%)	PIC
Me2-Em5	5	2	40,0	0,25
Me7-Em1	8	2	25,0	0,44
Me9-Em6	3	0	0,0	0,01
Me9-Em8	6	2	33,3	0,25
Me9-Em11	6	1	16,7	0,46
Me11-Em1	5	2	40,0	0,33
Me11-Em2	8	2	25,0	0,48
Me11-Em5	4	1	25,0	0,25
Me11-Em8	6	3	50,0	0,39
Me12-Em3	5	0	0,0	0,11
Me12-Em4	5	3	60,0	0,28
Me12-Em8	3	1	33,3	0,14
Me13-Em12	6	1	16,7	0,43
Me13-Em14	9	4	44,4	0,51
Max.			60,0	0,5
Min.			0,0	0,01
Mean			29,3	0,3

When the dendrogram created with the combination of 14 SRAP primers was examined, a similarity between genotypes was determined between 0.67 and 1.00. The resulting dendrogram formed two main groups, and only genotype 25 was included in the first group. Other genotypes were included in the second group and its subgroups. According to this dendrogram, the most similar genotypes were genotypes 12 and 13. Additionally, genotypes 29 and 30 were found to be highly identical (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dendrogram created with the combination of 14 SRAP primers of Cirgalan Pepper genotypes

In recent years, Turkey's local pepper populations have been collected, characterized, and included in both production and breeding programs. In a study conducted by Başak [29], a characterization study was carried out on 99 green pepper genotypes collected from Kırşehir province and surrounding villages in terms of a total of 48 agronomic and morphological features determined for pepper by IPGRI and UPOV. According to the morphological and agronomic characteristics examined, the genotypes were divided into 15 groups in the dendrogram. As a result of the cluster analysis, it has been reported that the genotypes coded S1, S2, S62, S3, S9, S67, and TR69737 are the most distant genotypes from each other regarding agronomic and morphological characteristics.

On the other hand, Karakurt et al. [24] carried out molecular characterization with SSR (Simple Sequence Repeats) markers to determine the genetic diversity of different pepper genotypes, and according to the results, pepper genotypes were divided into two main groups in the UPGMA dendrogram obtained with SSR markers. The first main group was divided into two subgroups. The first subgroup included Vezir, Üçburun, Acıburun, Yükselince, Anadolu, Serenad, and Hayfa Chile, and the second subgroup included Jalomex. On the other hand, Ergenekon and Kanyon genotypes were included

in the second leading group. Vezir- Üçburun and Yükselince- Anadolu varieties are groups of similar groups, showing similar characteristics in the examined SSR regions.

The study used for the molecular characterization of 30 capia, stuffed, pointed, and green pepper varieties was characterized using 6 SSR loci. According to the results, it was concluded that there was no wide molecular variation in pepper varieties in terms of the examined regions, and the varieties showed similarities between 0.77-1.00 in terms of the areas examined [25]. The study examined the molecular and morphological characteristics of 28 local eggplant varieties, collectively known as "Yamula Patlıcanı," widely cultivated in Turkey. It also analyzed three varieties of Kemer peppers and one variety of Manisa peppers. The molecular studies revealed that the polymorphism ratio was 77.36% for ISSR and 73.72% for SRAP. According to the SRAP marker analysis, the genetic similarity among the genotypes varied between 0.68 and 0.99 [26]. In the study by Okay [27] with 35 inbred and purified qualified pepper breeding lines and 3 commercial pepper varieties, genetic characterization of pepper lines was made using 19 SRAP primer combinations. The similarity index values of the pepper lines used in the study were reported to vary between 0.35 and 0.97. Another study aimed to conduct the molecular characterization of some Elazığ native peppers belonging to the *Capsicum annum* species. For molecular characterization, 9 POX markers were used, 105 bands were obtained using POX markers, and 60 of them were polymorphic[28].

CONCLUSION

The wide variation is obtained in the characterization studies of local genotypes in Turkey. This variation may have been because the pepper had open pollination and self-pollination. According to the data obtained in this study, quite a wide variation was obtained due to molecular (SRAP) characterization performed on 23 Cırgalan pepper genotypes and 8 control genotypes selected from Kayseri province and its districts. According to molecular data, it was determined that there was a genetic difference between the control genotypes and the Cırgalan pepper genotypes and that there was also a difference between the Cırgalan pepper genotypes. The variation identified in the findings obtained from this study aligns with the studies mentioned above. A wide variation has been obtained in Cırgalan pepper, and it seems possible to increase the productivity and quality of these types in Kayseri province and its surroundings by developing new varieties of this pepper type using this variation.

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